
 AN EXTENSION OF A FORMULA OF JOVOVIC

Shane Chern

Dept. of Mathematics, Penn State University, University Park, Pennsylvania
 shanechern@psu.edu

Received: 12/28/18, Revised: 4/29/19, Accepted: 8/3/19, Published: 9/30/19

Abstract

Let $u > v$ be two positive integers and c be an integer. In this note, we give a closed form of the number of subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ of vn elements whose sum is congruent to c modulo n . This extends a formula of Vladeta Jovovic.

1. Introduction

A result of Erdős, Ginzburg and Ziv [3] states as follows.

Theorem. *Each set of $2n - 1$ integers contains some subset of n elements the sum of which is a multiple of n .*

In particular, if the set of $2n - 1$ integers is $\{1, 2, \dots, 2n - 1\}$, Vladeta Jovovic conjectured a closed form of the number of such n -member subsets, denoted by $s(n)$:

$$s(n) = \frac{(-1)^n}{2n} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \binom{2d}{d}, \quad (1)$$

where the summation runs over all positive divisors of n , $\phi(\cdot)$ is Euler's totient function, and $\binom{2d}{d}$ is the d -th central binomial coefficient. This formula was later confirmed by Max Alekseyev [1], whose proof relies on heavy computation on trigonometric functions. We remark that $s(n)$ is sequence A145855 in the OEIS [5].

In this note, we not only provide an alternative proof of (1) that avoids the computation involving trigonometric functions in Alekseyev's proof, but also give the following extension.

Theorem 1.1. *Let $u > v$ be two positive integers and c be an integer. Let n be a positive integer. If $s(u, v; c; n)$ counts the number of subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ of*

vn elements whose sum is congruent to c modulo n , then

$$s(u, v; c; n) = \begin{cases} \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \mu\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right) \frac{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)}{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right)} \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \mu\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right) \frac{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)}{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right)} \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd,} \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where $\mu(\cdot)$ is the Möbius function and $\phi(\cdot)$ is Euler's totient function. We also adopt the convention that $\gcd(0, n) = n$.

3-mem.	$\Sigma \text{ mod } 3$	3-mem.	$\Sigma \text{ mod } 3$	2-mem.	$\Sigma \text{ mod } 2$	2-mem.	$\Sigma \text{ mod } 2$
{1, 2, 3}	0	{1, 4, 5}	1	{1, 2}	1	{2, 4}	0
{1, 2, 4}	1	{2, 3, 4}	0	{1, 3}	0	{2, 5}	1
{1, 2, 5}	2	{2, 3, 5}	1	{1, 4}	1	{3, 4}	1
{1, 3, 4}	2	{2, 4, 5}	2	{1, 5}	0	{3, 5}	0
{1, 3, 5}	0	{3, 4, 5}	0	{2, 3}	1	{4, 5}	1

(a) $n = 3, u = 2, v = 1$

(b) $n = 2, u = 3, v = 1$

4-mem.	$\Sigma \text{ mod } 2$
{1, 2, 3, 4}	0
{1, 2, 3, 5}	1
{1, 2, 4, 5}	0
{1, 3, 4, 5}	1
{2, 3, 4, 5}	0

(c) $n = 2, u = 3, v = 2$

Table 1: 2-, 3- and 4-Member subsets of $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$

In Table 1, we give three examples to illustrate Theorem 1.1. Here “ k -mem.” means k -member subsets of $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and “ $\Sigma \text{ mod } d$ ” means the sum of elements in the subset modulo d .

Examples. (i). Let $n = 3, u = 2$ and $v = 1$. Then we are considering 3-member subsets of $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$, which are listed in Table 1a. On the other hand, it follows from Theorem 1.1 that $s(2, 1; 0; 3) = 4, s(2, 1; 1; 3) = 3$ and $s(2, 1; 2; 3) = 3$.

(ii). Let $n = 2, u = 3$ and $v = 1$. Then we are considering 2-member subsets of $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. One may compute from Theorem 1.1 that $s(3, 1; 0; 2) = 4$ and $s(3, 1; 1; 2) = 6$. The two values match with Table 1b.

(iii). Let $n = 2$, $u = 3$ and $v = 2$. Then we are considering 4-member subsets of $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. It can be computed by Theorem 1.1 that $s(3, 2; 0; 2) = 3$ and $s(3, 2; 1; 2) = 2$, which, again, match with Table 1c.

Further, if we take $c = 0$ and 1 respectively in (2), we get the following corollaries.

Corollary 1.2. *Let $u > v$ be two positive integers. The number of subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ of vn elements which sum to a multiple of n equals*

$$\begin{cases} \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Corollary 1.3. *Let $u > v$ be two positive integers. The number of subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ of vn elements which sum to one more than a multiple of n equals*

$$\begin{cases} \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \mu\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \mu\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \binom{ud}{vd} & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Remark. One may further take $u = 2$ and $v = 1$ in (3) to deduce Jovovic’s formula (1).

2. Proof of the Main Result

We begin with some combinatorial arguments. Let $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{vn}\}$ be a subset of $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ with $1 \leq x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{vn} \leq un - 1$. For each $1 \leq i \leq vn$, we write $x_i = x'_i + i$. It follows that $0 \leq x'_1 \leq x'_2 \leq \dots \leq x'_{vn} \leq (u - v)n - 1$. Hence, the numbers $x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_{vn}$ uniquely determine a partition with the largest part not exceeding $(u - v)n - 1$ and the number of parts not exceeding vn . Here, as usual, a partition of a nonnegative integer N is a weakly decreasing sequence of positive integers (which are called the parts) that sum to N .

It is a standard result (cf. Chapter 3 in [2]) in the theory of partitions that the generating function of partitions into at most M parts, each not exceeding L , is given by the conventional q -binomial coefficient

$$\begin{bmatrix} M + L \\ M \end{bmatrix}_q := \prod_{k=1}^M \frac{1 - q^{L+k}}{1 - q^k} = \prod_{k=1}^L \frac{1 - q^{M+k}}{1 - q^k}.$$

We remark that it is indeed a polynomial in q of degree LM . Hence, the generating function of partitions with the largest part not exceeding $(u - v)n - 1$ and the number of parts not exceeding vn is

$$R(q) = \sum_{m=0}^{vn((u-v)n-1)} r(m)q^m := \left[\begin{matrix} un - 1 \\ vn \end{matrix} \right]_q. \tag{5}$$

Let $G(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} g(n)q^n$ be a formal power series. From the orthogonality of roots of unity, we have the following identity

$$\sum_{\substack{n \geq 0 \\ n \equiv h \pmod{H}}} g(n)q^n = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{\ell=1}^H e^{-\frac{2\pi i h \ell}{H}} G\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{H}} q\right). \tag{6}$$

To determine the expression of $s(u, v; c; n)$, we notice that $\sum_{i=1}^{vn} x_i \equiv c \pmod{n}$ is equivalent to

$$\sum_{i=1}^{vn} x'_i \equiv \begin{cases} c \pmod{n} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{n}{2} + c \pmod{n} & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd,} \end{cases}$$

since

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + 2 + \dots + vn &= \frac{vn(vn + 1)}{2} \\ &\equiv \begin{cases} 0 \pmod{n} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{n}{2} \pmod{n} & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} s(u, v; c; n) &= \begin{cases} \sum_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \equiv c \pmod{n}}}^{vn((u-v)n-1)} r(m) & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \sum_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \equiv \frac{n}{2} + c \pmod{n}}}^{vn((u-v)n-1)} r(m) & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n e^{-\frac{2\pi i c \ell}{n}} R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right) & \text{if } n \text{ is odd or } n \text{ and } v \text{ are both even,} \\ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n (-1)^\ell e^{-\frac{2\pi i c \ell}{n}} R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right) & \text{if } n \text{ is even and } v \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

In the next lemma, we evaluate $R(e^{2\pi i \ell/n})$.

Lemma 2.1. *Let ℓ be a positive integer. Then*

$$R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right) = \frac{u-v}{u} \binom{u \cdot \gcd(\ell, n)}{v \cdot \gcd(\ell, n)}. \tag{8}$$

Proof. Recall that

$$R(q) = \left[\begin{matrix} un-1 \\ vn \end{matrix} \right]_q = \prod_{k=1}^{(u-v)n-1} \frac{1-q^{vn+k}}{1-q^k}.$$

Hence,

$$R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right) = \prod_{k=1}^{(u-v)n-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}} \frac{1-q^{vn+k}}{1-q^k},$$

where

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}} \frac{1-q^{vn+k}}{1-q^k} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right)^k \neq 1, \\ \frac{vn+k}{k} & \text{if } \left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right)^k = 1. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, $\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right)^k = 1$ implies that n divides $k\ell$.

For convenience, we write $n = n'd$ and $\ell = \ell'd$ where $d = \gcd(\ell, n)$. Then $n \mid k\ell$ is equivalent to $n' \mid k$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{k=1}^{(u-v)n-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}} \frac{1-q^{vn+k}}{1-q^k} &= \prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \equiv 0 \pmod{n'}}}^{(u-v)n-1} \frac{vn+k}{k} = \prod_{k'=1}^{(u-v)d-1} \frac{vn+k'n'}{k'n'} \\ &= \prod_{k'=1}^{(u-v)d-1} \frac{vd+k'}{k'} = \binom{ud-1}{(u-v)d-1} = \frac{u-v}{u} \binom{ud}{vd}, \end{aligned}$$

where in the second identity we set $k = k'n'$.

Consequently, we have that

$$R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i \ell}{n}}\right) = \frac{u-v}{u} \binom{ud}{vd} = \frac{u-v}{u} \binom{u \cdot \gcd(\ell, n)}{v \cdot \gcd(\ell, n)},$$

which is our desired result. □

If n is odd or n and v are both even, then it follows from (7) and (8) that

$$\begin{aligned} s(u, v; c; n) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i\ell}{n}}\right) \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{\ell=1}^n e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} \begin{pmatrix} u \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \\ v \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \begin{pmatrix} ud \\ vd \end{pmatrix} \sum_{\substack{\ell=1 \\ \gcd(\ell, n)=d}}^n e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \begin{pmatrix} ud \\ vd \end{pmatrix} \sum_{\substack{\ell'=1 \\ \gcd(\ell', \frac{n}{d})=1}}^{\frac{n}{d}} \exp\left(-\frac{2\pi ic\ell'}{n/d}\right) \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} \mu\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right) \frac{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)}{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right)} \begin{pmatrix} ud \\ vd \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

where in the last identity we use the following evaluation of Ramanujan’s sum (cf. Theorem 272 in [4])

$$c_q(m) := \sum_{\substack{\ell=1 \\ \gcd(\ell, q)=1}}^q \exp\left(\frac{2\pi im\ell}{q}\right) = \mu\left(\frac{q}{\gcd(m, q)}\right) \frac{\phi(q)}{\phi\left(\frac{q}{\gcd(m, q)}\right)}.$$

To show the second case of the main result, we have that if n is even and v is odd, then

$$s(u, v; c; n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n (-1)^\ell e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} R\left(e^{\frac{2\pi i\ell}{n}}\right) = \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{\ell=1}^n (-1)^\ell e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} \begin{pmatrix} u \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \\ v \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since n is even, we see that ℓ and $\gcd(\ell, n)$ have the same parity. Hence, $(-1)^\ell = (-1)^{\gcd(\ell, n)}$. Following the same argument as above, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} s(u, v; c; n) &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{\ell=1}^n (-1)^{\gcd(\ell, n)} e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} \begin{pmatrix} u \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \\ v \cdot \gcd(\ell, n) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \begin{pmatrix} ud \\ vd \end{pmatrix} \sum_{\substack{\ell=1 \\ \gcd(\ell, n)=d}}^n e^{-\frac{2\pi ic\ell}{n}} \\ &= \frac{u-v}{un} \sum_{d|n} (-1)^d \mu\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right) \frac{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)}{\phi\left(\frac{n}{d \cdot \gcd(c, \frac{n}{d})}\right)} \begin{pmatrix} ud \\ vd \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

We therefore arrive at the desired result.

3. Closing Remarks

If we replace the set $\{1, 2, \dots, un - 1\}$ in Theorem 1.1 by an arbitrary set of $un - 1$ consecutive integers, say $\{a + 1, a + 2, \dots, a + un - 1\}$, the formula in (2) still holds. In fact, if $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{vn}\}$ (with $x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{vn}$) is a subset, we may put $x_i = x'_i + a + i$ for each $1 \leq i \leq vn$ and then carry out the same procedure as in Section 2.

For a general set \mathcal{S} of $2n - 1$ integers in the theorem of Erdős, Ginzburg and Ziv stated at the beginning of this note, there seems to be no closed form that enumerates the number of n -member subsets whose elements sum to a multiple of n . Apparently, our approach would fail for general \mathcal{S} as the initial combinatorial argument in Section 2 now does not make sense. On the other hand, following Alekseyev [1], we know that the number of such subsets is

$$-1 + \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \prod_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left(1 + \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i(j + ks)}{n}\right) \right).$$

However, there is no obvious approach that can simplify this expression.

It would be an intriguing problem to find other examples of \mathcal{S} that give nice closed forms of the number of the desired n -member subsets, or even may lead to parallel extensions like our Theorem 1.1.

Acknowledgements. I would like to thank the referee for helpful suggestions.

References

- [1] M. Alekseyev, Proof of Jovovic's formula, unpublished manuscript (2008). Available at <http://oeis.org/A145855/a145855.txt>.
- [2] G. E. Andrews, *The Theory of Partitions*, Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., Reading, 1976.
- [3] P. Erdős, A. Ginzburg, and A. Ziv, Theorem in the additive number theory, *Bull. Res. Council. Israel Sect. F Math. Phys.* **10F** (1961), no. 1, 41–43.
- [4] G. H. Hardy and E. M. Wright, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers. Sixth Edition*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2008.
- [5] N. J. A. Sloane, On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <http://oeis.org>.